

IN SITU THERMAL CYCLING OF A SHORT FIBER METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Thermal cycling (TC) is one of the primary damaging modes in metal matrix composites (MMC). The mismatch of thermal expansion coefficient (MTEC) between components results in plastic strains at the interface. In situ TC, in transmission electron microscopy, was used to visualize the mismatch problem and the dynamics of the microstructural and damage evolution. Investigation was conducted on a squeeze cast Al-based MMC. The effects of number of cycles was studied with TC conducted between 100-350°C in about 3 minutes. A total of 1250 cycles were performed. Observations were recorded on video tape. A globularization of the second phase was observed as well as dynamic recovery after repeated heating and cooling. Short crack propagation and growth of precipitates at the crack tip was observed.

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites (DRMMC)s are promising materials for high temperature applications. Under isothermal temperature or cyclic changes in temperature, differential expansion between components generates high strains at the reinforcement/matrix interface which could lead to dimensional instabilities or damage accumulation[1-3].

This fundamental problem is difficult to observe as TEM observations are normally done at room temperature and cannot identify the mechanisms occurring at high temperature. Furthermore, sample removal from the bulk in order to follow the microstructural evolution can become very time consuming[4]. Thus, in situ thermal cycling (TC), in transmission electron microscopy (TEM), was used as a unique technique to remedy this problem and to investigate the dynamic evolution of the microstructure, deformation and damage mechanisms under TC.

Thermal cycling was performed on an Al7Si4Cu/15% Saffil δ -alumina short fiber composite between 100 and 350°C in about 3 minutes up to a total of 1250 cycles. In situ observation was performed up to 325 cycles in the microscope while cycles between 325 and 1250 cycles were performed both in a vacuum chamber and the microscope. This chamber allows to reproduce the exact cycling conditions as in TEM for overnight testing. Direct observation were recorded on video tape in a 200 kV conventionnal TEM. In our previous work, in situ TC was conducted up to 265 cycles showing the beginning of the evolution from tangle dislocation structure in the matrix to subgrain boundary structures. Cracking of intermetallic phases was also observed. In this study, the evolution of the dislocation structure and mostly the crack propagation was followed up to 1250 cycles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As previously shown in MMCs exposed to temperature, a high density of dislocation is present at fiber matrix interface (fig. 1)[1-7]. The mechanism of dislocation punchout on cooling and dislocations moving towards the interface while heating were observed and experimental details are given in [7]. Figure 2 and 3 show the subgrain structure which was seen after 250 cycles compared to the substructure observed after 1250 cycles. The subgrains are getting finer as dipoles annihilate to produce thinner boundaries. This process was shown to be dynamic recovery and subgrain growth occurred even though the size could not be measured as subgrains are not all contained in the TEM samples.

Figure 1. High density and tangled interfacial dislocations in as-cast MMCs.

Figure 2. Subgrain structure after 250 thermal cycles.

Figure 3. Subgrain structure after 1250 thermal cycles.

A crack was observed after 250 TC[7]. The state of crack propagation seen after 265 cycles is shown in figure 4 as was shown in our previous work. The crack has propagated through the next nearby second phases. Figures 5 to 9 show the evolution of the crack tip for 300, 500, 750, 1000 and 1250 cycles, where stress driven diffusion was observed. The Al_2Cu precipitate has grown at the crack tip parallel to the crack path. Crack tip blunting was observed at the other end of the crack. Only after 500 cycles, the crack propagated at this end were precipitate growth was also visible.

Figure 4. Cracked intermetallic after 265 cycles between 100 and 350°C.

Figure 5. Cracked intermetallic after 300 cycles between 100 and 350°C.

Figure 6. Cracked intermetallic after 500 cycles between 100 and 350°C.

Figure 7. Cracked intermetallic after 750 cycles between 100 and 350°C.

Figure 8. Cracked intermetallic after 1000 cycles between 100 and 350°C.

Figure 9. Cracked intermetallic after 1250 cycles between 100 and 350°C.

Precipitates located at the crack tip tends to change their morphology and follow the crack path by diffusion process. Damaging of MMCs by thermal cycling is a strain based mechanism. The mismatch strain *viz.* the strain induced by the difference between the thermal expansion coefficient of matrix and fibers can cause local stress concentration and cyclic viscoplasticity of the matrix leading to a low cycle fatigue process. Localized mechanical behavior of a representative element of volume composed of the fiber and matrix can be described by an out-of-phase thermal and mechanical cycle.

The precipitate as grown at the crack tip parallele to the crack propagation direction. The precipitate width reported as a function of the cycle number in figure 10 shows a fast increase followed by a slower constant rate of growth after about 400 cycles. This acceleration was seen over a length of about 400 nm. The crack propagation was also reported as a function of cycle numbers (figure 11) showing the same type of behavior. The crack propagated faster in the first 400 cycles (15 nm/cycle) and then advanced at constant rate (about 2 nm/cycle).

Figure 10. Stress driven precipitate growth as a function of cycle number.

Figure 11. Crack propagation as a function of cycle number.

The initial increase observed in both crack propagation and precipitate growth could be explained by a complex stress state in the matrix ahead of the crack tip. In fact, during cooling the matrix is put under tension by 2 fibers in the vicinity in orthogonal position beside the crack. The MTEC stress from the fibers was the main driving force for crack propagation. Large silicon particles and Al₂Cu precipitates have also their own mismatch with the matrix. These mismatch generate additional tensile stresses that could increase propagation and diffusion at the crack tip. Under such complex localized loading the Al₂Cu precipitate tends to grow along the crack path towards the stress concentration zone. The distance over which the a faster crack propagation and precipitate growth was observed, corresponds approximately to the precipitate diameter.

CONCLUSION

In situ TEM thermal cycling was conducted on a 15% alumina short fiber Al₇Si₄Cu composite. Extended TC led to dynamic recovery mechanisms where subgrains became finer and well defined. Crack propagation was observed. The crack propagated through next nearby second phases and stress driven diffusion was observed at the crack tip. The Al₂Cu precipitate at the crack tip tends to follow the crack path towards the stress concentration zone by diffusion process.

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